

Emerging Trends in ICCT as Universal Technology for Survival, Sustainability, Differentiation, Monopoly and Development

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Abstract:

Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) and Nanotechnology (NT) are recently identified Universal technologies of the 21st century and are expected to substantially contribute to the development of the society by solving the basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human beings. In this paper, the possibilities of using ICCT and its underlying ten most important emerging technologies like Artificial intelligence, Big data & business analytics, Cloud computing, Digital marketing, 3D printing, Internet of Things, Online ubiquitous education, Optical computing, Storage technology, and Virtual & Augmented Reality are explored. The emerging trends of applications of the above underlying technologies of ICCT in the primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary industry sectors of the society are discussed, analysed, and predicted using a newly developed predictive analysis model. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of such technologies to fulfill the desires of human beings to lead luxurious and comfort lifestyle from various stakeholders point of views are identified and discussed. The paper also focuses on the potential applications of ICCT as a strategic tool for survival, sustainability, differentiation, and development of various business models. Finally, the various breakthroughs expected in the above underlying technologies along with their timeframe are predicted and discussed.

Keywords : ICCT, Universal technology, Emerging trends, Information science & technology, ABCD analysis, Industry sectors, ICCT as strategic tool.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Technology is generally considered as an application of science and is used to solve different problems in the society with an intension to make human life comfortable and enjoyable. Many technologies have been identified as General-Purpose Technologies due to their abilities to solve problems in many sectors in the society. Such technologies are used by many branches of engineering to solve or simplify the problems of those fields [1]. General Purpose Technologies' (GPT) are developed due to the ability of killer applications in solving problems in many industrial sectors. Examples for such killer applications which have been

converted into GPT's are steam engine, railroad, interchangeable parts, electricity, semiconductor electronics, material handling, mechanization, control theory (automation), the automobile, the computer, the Internet, Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT), and Nanotechnology (NT). But out of above killer application technologies, only two technologies further emerged as Universal technologies of 21st century. In this paper, we have considered and discussed the major underlying technologies of ICCT and their emerging trends of applications on the primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary industry sectors of the society using a newly developed predictive analysis model [2].

2. OBJECTIVES :

The objectives of this conceptual analysis paper are to study the emerging trends in Information Communication and Computation Technology under the following issues :

- (1) To describe ICCT and its underlying emerging technologies which are making ICCT as Universal General Purpose Technology.
- (2) To study the important underlying technologies under the umbrella ICCT and their effect on solving problems related to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human beings of the society.
- (3) To analyse the emerging trends of applications of the above underlying technologies of ICCT in the primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary industry sectors of the society using my newly developed predictive analysis model.
- (4) To identify the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of such technologies to fulfill the desires of human beings to lead a luxurious and comfortable lifestyle from various stakeholders point of views.

3. UNIVERSAL TECHNOLOGIES :

The general purpose technologies (GPT's) used in many industries are characterized by (1) their pervasiveness where they have an inherent potential of solving many problems, (2) proneness to technical improvements, and (3) complements innovations, meaning that through research and development the productivity in many industry sectors increases [1, 2]. It is found that many killer applications transformed into GPT's and many of them are making an impact only in one or two related industries and replaced by other innovative technologies or die-down eventually [2]. But it is noticed that two General Purpose Technologies identified as Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT), and Nanotechnology (NT) have shown their abilities to solve both basic problems and advanced need of the society and hence have shown their contribution towards creating a techno-society and based on further progress and spread of such technologies to every dimension of human life to reach the ultimate level of civilization in or around this earth. Hence these two futuristic technologies which have potential ability for solving problems related to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human beings of the society and are named as Universal technologies of the 21st century [2].

In order to emerge as universal technology, a GPT should have following properties :

- (1) Pervasiveness – The GPT should spread to many sectors.
- (2) Improvement – The GPT should get better over time and, hence, should keep lowering the costs of its users.
- (3) Innovation Opportunity – The GPT should support to invent and produce new products or processes.

Whole eras of technical progress and growth appear to be driven by a few 'General Purpose Technologies' (GPT's), such as the steam engine, the electric motor, and semiconductors.

Economist Richard Lipsey and Kenneth Carlaw of University of British Columbia, Canada suggested that any technology transforms into GPT if it follows four criteria :

- (1) GPT is a single, recognisable generic technology.
- (2) Initially GPT has much scope for improvement but comes to be widely used across the economy.
- (3) GPT has many different uses in many areas to solve problems or to provide comfortability.
- (4) GPT creates many spill over effects to spread its base to many sectors.

Those General Purpose Technologies useful in solving problems related to Basic Needs, Advanced Wants, Dreamy Desires, and having applications more or less in all industry sectors are called as Universal Technologies.

4. UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES OF ICCT :

4.1 ICCT as GPT :

Recently it is argued that information generation, communication, processing, storing, and retrieval are the parts of a single system called Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) and is considered as an integrated version of Information Communication Technology (ICT) and Computer Technology (CT). It is also observed that ICCT shows all the three characteristics of GPT : Pervasiveness, Growth, and Innovation opportunity. In the 21st century, ICCT is grown and spread its roots to all industries and industry sectors from A to Z due to its pervasiveness property [2]. The Improvement and Innovation spawning properties of Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) as general purpose technology are created major stake holding areas including Artificial intelligence, Big data & business analytics, Cloud computing Technology, Digital marketing Technology, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IOT), Online Ubiquitous education & Training Technology, Optical computing Technology, Information Storage technology, and Virtual & Augmented Reality.

Fig. 1 : Block diagram representing ten most useful futuristic underlying technologies of ICCT

Cellular agriculture and 3D food printing, the two new technologies that are expected to change the way people will source food from in near future. These technologies lead to animal-free, cultured & plant based versions of meat, milk, eggs and leather or in other words, they are milk without cow, eggs without hen and meat without animal.

Table 1 : ICCT underlying technologies, their objectives, and ultimate goal

S. No	Underlying Technologies of ICCT	Objectives	Ultimate Goal
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	Performing by thinking and doing things better than human beings	Ideal artificial brain & connecting brains with computers
2	Big data and Business Analytics	Developing effective information using hidden patterns, unknown correlations, market trends, and customer preferences to help organizations for making better business decisions	Ideal Business prediction
3	Cloud Computing Technology	Using computer infrastructure at cost effective and optimum level from ubiquitous location	Ideal Computer [3]
4	Digital Business & Marketing	Ubiquitous mobile business and e-marketing using digital and internet technology	Ideal Business [4, 5]
5	3D printing Technology	Preparing three dimensional structures from a digital file. This is achieved using additive processes using less material than traditional <i>manufacturing methods</i>	Ideal Production of components & Devices
6	Internet of Things (IOT)	Interconnection and integration of the physical world and the cyber space remotely to control the devices from distance	Ideal interconnection & Control
7	Online Ubiquitous Education & Training	Education for everybody irrespective of location, age, economic level using technology	Ideal education system [6, 7]
8	Optical Computing Technology	High speed data processing	Ideal Computers [8, 9]
9	Information Storage Technology	Huge amount of information storage in a small region using suitable technology	Ideal storage system
10	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Virtual reality is an immersion experience which gives the physical world feelings	Ideal virtual experience [10]

Table 2 : Basic needs and ideal solutions

S.	Basic Needs of	Best solutions	Supporting Technologies
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No.	the society		
1	Nutritious Food	Artificial Food	Cellular agriculture, 3D food printing, Artificial photosynthesis etc.
2	Drinking water	Potable water	Nanotechnology
3	Transportation	Zero cost transportation	Solar technology, Energy storage technology, Nanotechnology, Virtual reality
4	Energy	Free energy from renewable sources	Solar technology, Energy storage technology, Nanotechnology
5	Shelter	Low cost, safe, and durable shelter called smart home	Nanotechnology, IOT, 3D printing
6	Education	Ubiquitous education	Wireless technology, Multimedia, and Internet technologies
7	Health	Quick solutions to all health related deceases	AI, IOT, Nano & Bio Technology
8	Long life	Prolonged life span of individuals	Bio-technology, Genetic engineering,

4.1 Artificial intelligence Technology:

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science which focuses on the creation of intelligent machines which can mimic the decisions of human beings. The primary objective of AI technology is develop machines which can think and do things better than human beings. The main functions of artificial intelligence machines are to recognize the environment such as speech recognition, Learning, Planning, Problem solving, and hence decision making. Artificial intelligence machine mimics cognitive functions of human beings associated with other human minds, such as learning & memorising and decision making for problem solving. ICCT has created a platform for AI to be introduced and developed for adding intelligent thinking components in electronic systems used in any industrial sectors [11]. Artificial intelligence has its applications in almost all industries in primary sector, secondary sectors, tertiary sectors and quaternary sector.

4.2 Big data & business analytics :

The emerging subfield of ICCT named big data and business analytics focus on handling huge amount of data continuously generated in any business or data capturing process and analyses it using various quantitative analytical techniques and mathematical models to study the pattern and descriptive information, predictive information, and prescriptive information for supporting the decision makers to take optimum decisions to the problems related to future aspects of the business. Predictive analytics in various functional areas like Marketing analytics, Retail Analytics (Customer Analytics / Supply Chain Analytics), Pricing Analytics, Financial analytics, Social media analytics, sports analytics, and Healthcare analytics are finding importance in the business environment for effective decision making. Further Prescriptive Analytics for optimizing the decisions with multiple objectives / portfolio

analytics, optimizing complex decisions / sales force analytics, and Retail Analytics etc are also have futuristic impact on effective business decisions [4-7].

4.3 Cloud computing :

Cloud computing is one of the advances in computer technology and is uses information communication technology as well. Due to the ubiquity of cloud computing facility with flexibility in scaling it has become an important topic of research and provides the value for computing processes in the business. The cloud computing model also provides a most important application called Business Intelligence (BI) for effective decision making in business processes via the Internet. Cloud computing model allows to offer both hardware as well as software to process the data online as a rental service. Thus, cloud computing model has three variations as Software as a Service (SaaS), Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) and Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) to provide ubiquitous computing service solutions to the business. The cloud computing solution to any business will allow companies to reduce their investment cost and maintenance cost for without compromising to have access to BI solution which will give the business an edge on their competition. Cloud computing is subfield of the Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT).

4.4 Digital Business & Marketing :

ICCT created a new business model called E-business/ M-business model. This model consists of ubiquitous selling proposition. *Digital marketing* is the *marketing* of products or services using *digital* technologies as per such new business model using mainly on the Internet, but also including mobile phones, display advertising, and any other *digital* medium. At a high level, *digital marketing* refers to advertising delivered through *digital* channels such as search engines, websites, social media, email, and mobile apps. Digital marketing is emerged as an essential future marketing activity using ICCT general purpose technology.

4.5 3D printing :

3D printing is an ICCT application where various materials are joined or solidified using various processes under the control of computer to create a three-dimensional object. In 3D printing, an object is created by laying down successive layers of material until the object is created. 3D printing can be divided into metal, fabrics, bio and a whole host of other industries with many applications in many industries worldwide. 3D printing is a variant of ICCT general purpose technology and has wide scope in various industrial automation and home automation processes. 3D printing technology is expected to revolutionise the material fabrication processes. 3D printing comprises of many other technologies along with ICCT. Some of the 3D printers make use of nanomaterials and nanocomposites for anything, anywhere manufacturing.

4.6 Internet of Things :

It is a network of various electronic, computing, and optical devices/objects including human beings connected virtually by means of internet or intranet for enabling them to send and receive data and information. These objects are provided with unique identifiers (UIDs) and are capable to transfer data and information over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction by using IOT technology. Such a connection of physical things/objects to the Internet makes it possible to access remote sensor data and to control the physical world from a distance. The mash-up of captured data with data retrieved from other sources, eg, with data that is contained in the Web, gives rise to new synergistic

services that go beyond the services that can be provided by an isolated embedded system. Internet-of-Things (IoT) is not in any new disruptive technology but is the pervasive deployment and innovation of ICCT.

4.7 Online ubiquitous education :

To provide education to everybody, transformation of traditional campus based education system into Massive Online Open Courses (MOOC) system is essential. Even though initially MOOC is considered as complementary to traditional campus based education HE system, as time progress, it may replace campus based HE system completely. Higher education focus on enhancing knowledge, skills, experience, and hence confidence to make innovations and better decisions can be offered equally effective through online using wireless video channels. Ubiquitous online education offered through multidisciplinary areas using simulation may out pass the traditional laboratory based education in HE system. The other underlying ICCT technologies also support online ubiquitous education system to make it more effective, efficient and easily accessible system for everybody without their geographical locations and economical conditions. Some of such growing brands include EDX, COUSERA, NPTEL, SWAYAM, etc.

4.8 Optical computing :

High speed computers based on optical signal switching and optical signal processing are expected to breakthrough with their full potentials and capabilities using optical logic gates and flip-flops fabricated by nanocomposites are expected to breakthrough in this century. High speed computation and data storage using nanotechnology based optical computers are going to revolutionize the entire computer industry. Optical computation is joining both general purpose technologies of Nanotechnology and ICCT through the processes of design & production as well as operation & applications respectively. Various optical principles like photo-refraction, optical spatial solitons, and optical logic gates are under considerations for building all-optical computers.

4.9 Information Storage Technology :

Information storage technology supports to develop devices to store & retrieve information in digital format. The trend in this field is to enhance the capability of devices to store huge amount of information in a small region at high speed and low cost. Various storage devices used and under consideration include Semiconductor Storage, Hologram Storage, Optical Storage, DNA Based Digital Storage, etc. which should have capability to store information in Terabytes, Petabytes, Exabytes, Zettabyte, and even Yottabyte in order to cater the forthcoming information storage applications.

4.10 Virtual & Augmented Reality :

Virtual reality is an artificial environment that is created with the help of computer-based software and presented to the user in such a way that the user suspends belief and accepts it as a real environment. On a computer, virtual reality is primarily experienced through two of the five senses: sight and sound. Currently, the virtual reality is mainly developed and used in simulated training and education as well as the simulated game environment. But it may further find its applications in many other areas including business as augmented reality and may enter the group of general purpose technology.

5. ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES IN INDUSTRY SECTORS :

ICCT has many applications in the many Industries and Industry sectors. Almost all Industries and industry sectors belonging to Primary, Secondary, Tertiary, and Quaternary Industry Sectors are basically supported by and get benefits from ICCT. In this section, some of the applications of ICCT in different industry sectors are discussed.

5.1. ICCT Underlying Technologies in Primary Industry Sector :

Industries and Industry sectors in primary sector are expected to get benefit from ICCT in to produce raw materials for other sectors.

Table 12 : Some applications of ICCT in Primary Industry Sector

S. No.	Underlying technologies of ICCT	Applications in Primary Industry Sector
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	AI based autonomous robots to handle essential agricultural tasks such as harvesting crops at a higher volume and faster pace than human labourers, to monitor crop and soil health, to study the environmental impacts on crop yield such as weather changes, precision farming, yield management etc. are seen as a weapon in doubling farmer income in near future [12].
2	Big data and Business Analytics	Smart farming, Precision agriculture, Big data analytics on reduction in fertilizer, cost savings, yield optimization, Seed quality management, Accurate crop prediction, Automated agriculture, Environmental awareness, Risk management, Food safety and spoilage prevention, etc. [13-14]
3	Cloud Computing Technology	Smart agriculture in which Agriculture-Cloud and IT offers expertise service to farmers regarding cultivation of crops, pricing, fertilizers, disease detail method of cure to be used etc. Scientists working at Agriculture research stations can add their discoveries, suggestions regarding modern techniques for cultivation, usage of fertilizers, can obtain cultivation history of the region etc. [15-17]
4	Digital Business & Marketing	E-marketing of agricultural products, Digital advertisements on global reach, Engage and interact with target audience and customer base [18].
5	3D printing Technology	Used in agriculture, forestry, and fishing industries for 3D printing based Food fabrication, Wood fabrication, recycling of fishing nets & ropes etc. [19-22].
6	Internet of Things (IOT)	Smart agriculture model, Environmental Monitoring and Control, Improving Agricultural Operations, Waste management, For fresh agricultural products, [23-25] .
7	Online Ubiquitous Education &	Agricultural education, Farm management, [26]

	Training	
8	Optical Computing Technology	Precision fish farming, High speed processors for information processing
9	Information Storage Technology	Enhanced data storage for high speed processing
10	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Agriculture farm management using Augmented reality, AR and VR for Cultivating the Garden etc. [27]

6. ICCT AS STRATEGIC TOOL :

- Survival Strategy – Black Ocean Strategy
- Sustainability Strategy – Green Ocean Strategy
- Differentiation Strategy – Red Ocean Strategy
- Monopoly Strategy – Blue Ocean Strategy
- Development Strategy – Yellow Ocean Strategy.

7. EXPECTED BREAKTHROUGHS & THEIR TIME FRAMES :

- Artificial Food
- Customized location focused rain & Reverse River
- Smart Home
- Renewable Energy at zero cost
- Online education for everybody
- Medicine for all Health problems leading to life span expansion and even immortality.

8. RESEARCH AGENDAS IN ICCT :

In each ICCT underlying Technologies :

- (1) Technology Issues
- (2) Application Issues
- (3) Product & Services Issues
- (4) Security Issues
- (5) IP Issues
- (6) Commercialization & Business Issues
- (7) Environmental Issues

9. CONCLUSION :

The emerging trends of applications of the above underlying technologies of ICCT in the primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary industry sectors of the society are discussed, analysed, and predicted using a newly developed predictive analysis model. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of such technologies to fulfill the desires of human beings to lead luxurious and comfort lifestyle from various stakeholders point of views are identified and discussed.

- The progress of ICCT underlying technologies is expected to solve basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of Human beings.
- ICCT is emerging as Universal GT to be necessary part of every industry.
- The 10 underlying technologies along with another Universal technology – nanotechnology, are expected to change the present challenges into new set of challenges.

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